

Asta Ja Resource Management Strategy for Economic Transformation in the Buddhist Economic Perspective

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Abstract: Human being in the new millennium performing different program through the ways of conducting millennium goal from 2001 to 2015 that announced and implemented by the United Nations Organization (UNO). After the completion of the targeted time-frame of MDG, the UNO, implementing the Sustainable Development Program announcing on 25 Sept 2015, for the achievement of various development goal within 2030. Consequently, the concept development designing for implementation also becoming an astounding matter to be achieved. For all the achievement of sustainable development Asta ja (Eight Ja) framework conceptualized from our own effort becoming a right innovation could be a faster development process if adopted globally. It goes through the way of becoming entrepreneur on their own venture would be rightly contributing to the society at large. Here to launch the utilization process of the resource, the learning of the Buddhist lesson Astanga Marga (Eightfold Path) could be of one to lead the society to make all disciplined working together skilfully. Concerning to manage the environment all the big and super powered nations must come to be leading the entire human world for maintenance of peace and prosperity in the globe. Ambition should be kept to produce every humanitarian product instead producing gun, missile, rocket and other equipment's for boosting war and threatening the human world. Concerning to this big power comes with big responsibilities. Therefore, everyone in this globe to come with working together for the protection of the globe, reducing global warming, through the way to be stopping the melting of glaciers from the Himalayas. Subsequently the species in the earth would be going on the verge of collapsing soon. So, the need of the time is to be working together for the maintenance of peace in the human world reducing global warming and environment hazards what becoming the urgent need of the time to be realized.

Keywords: Millennium and Sustainable development goal, global warming, Eight Ja Campaign, Astanga Marga learning.

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Chapter- I: Asta Ja Resource Management Strategy for Economic Transformation in the Buddhist Economic Perspective:

Introduction: Asta Ja now become a most popular concept within a short span of time since its inception in 2008, in the society. Specially, the concept is popular among the rural people involved in various incomes generating activities and aiming at to raise their living standard following the concept of Buddhist Economics, learning the lesson, Astanga Marga (Eight fold Path). At first, the concept of Jas was framed at the cognizance for the utilization of the resources in the discussion conducted in the ministry of finance during the time of Dr. Babauram Bhattarai, who was finance minister of new and progressive government after the peaceful settlement of Ten Years People's War. He was also the leader of Maoist who was holding the position of finance ministry becoming so ambitious to bring the economic transpiration in the country facilitating the people at large.

The new government was keenly initialed to make the nation a new one by raising a slogan to make New Nepal. Then the finance ministry started discussion inviting the intellectuals to design an effective program that may send to implement to launch production movement all over the country. Through the discussion among the intellectuals where this writer also one decided to explore Pancha Ja's (Five Ja) program with the objective of proper utilization of the resources mentioned in the Five Jas. The Five Ja, resources are Jal-water, Jamin-land, Jungle-forest, Jadibuti medicinal and aromatic herbs, and human resource, emphasizing that all mentioned resources must be properly identified to send them for production. So, as the concept Ja, to name the resources originated from the finance ministry of Nepal in 2008.

While the concept framed and started to design the program for economic prosperity of the nation, the group including myself again conducted a meeting and analyzed the Five Jas, what indicating to identify the resources. Then we conducted meeting decided to supplement three more jas, to the Five Ja. are so as : Jarajuri-plants, Jalabayu-climate, and Janawar-animal, to form Asta Ja (Eight Ja), for the identification of the resources that we all deriving from the nature. Accordingly the complete form of Asta Ja (Eight Ja) framework initialed to design the program for integrated development.

The movement became popular among the local community within very short span of time. Now it is demanding all over the country. Some more visitors and from different countries also liked much the concept. Accordingly, the political leaders from different parties also interested to help Asta Ja Abhiyan group (Eight Ja Movement Group). With all the positive surroundings the Asta Ja Abhiyan group encouraged to expand the activities in different districts in Nepal forming district and village committee to launch Asta Ja (Eight Ja) program. Specially, the valley committee gone forward to organized the awareness program in the three districts: Kathmandu, Lalitpur and Bhaktpur, of Kathmandu valley to increase the farm products systematically.

The Asta Ja Abhiyan group (Eight Ja Movement Group) planned to set some special team such as youth, women, specialists, to work for the production of different product and production management groups to carry out the productive sector effectively. Then also the research team found that the Asta Ja (Eight Ja) concept forwarding in different parts by forming committees in all over the country becoming an effective tool which will create an

environment to motivate the community people to work jointly to increase the production from that they may generate higher benefit from their systemic model of farming.

Earlier, people used to ask to the leaders to support to reduce their trouble for their household management instead working in their farming effectively becoming good-for-nothing to them. After the inception of the Asta Ja (Eight Ja) program, they became encouraged to go on farming with right modernization of the technique. Adopting the program the farmers even they used to be residing in the remote parts or the remote village there extending a new rays of hope to become happy afterwards, who used to be suffering long in their lives.

1.2 Economic System Adopted: Regarding all the aspect for the maintenance of peace in this globe in present days everyone in the entire world, becoming so much conscious to analyses the situation to find out the comfortable parts in the globe. Concerning to manage the desire of the people a leader leading to the society couldn't manage to meet so mounting aspiration of the people all over. Regarding all these there remain only a resilient solution becoming the economic system to be adopted properly. Consequently, the system previously adopted as of thinking that used to be bringing miracle changes in the social lives but all failed to achieve the goal of the system they were adopting. The system vitally explored is the capitalist one, with the effort of the richest and countries deserving super power in the world in the US and it's alliances just as UK, Australia, Canada, and the countries in the European Union but now interoperable failed to improve the socioeconomic system in the world. In the same way the next came to be adopted the social system, what aims to maintain equalization of the sharing of outcome, with the major participation of the labor. Karl Marx propounded the system but not much been exemplifying the well-developed society just to bring changes of the system of governance in the name of communism.

1.3 Buddhist Economic model: Analyzing both the system the new way of outcome urgently needed to improve the sociolect-economic spare in the world is now raising aspiration of the people is the Buddhist Economic System what was at first defined by the E.F. Shumacher in his book *Small is Beautiful*. Comparing the economic system of Catalysts and Buddhist there seems vast empirical divergence between both the system. Briefly acknowledging both the system as: capitalist demand maximization of profits and higher rate of return from the investment. Buddhist Economic System disagree the functional aspect of Capitalist Economy that has been just mentioned herewith. Because Buddhist Economic System emphasizes to maximize happiness, distribution of outcome of the effort equally among the people. Considering such the fundamental barriers the Buddhist Economic System if adopted would be more popular and social friendly, to what the intellectuals are advocating. As for instances Bhutan adopted system with gross peoples happiness, While no country practices a pure form of Buddhist economics, the country most closely associated with it is Bhutan, due to its official policy of measuring national progress through Gross National Happiness (GNH) instead of solely focusing GDP. Becoming the unique innovation that has been adopted by the United Nation Organizations Program publishing happiness Index of its 193 member countries. India adopted with it's Stage Socialism model of Buddhist Economic System, trying to equalize the outcome of the people combine effort. Likewise in Srilanka right cooperative model adopted in the name of Sarvodaya by the effort of a noble teacher A. T. Aryaratne. In Thailand Buddhist Economics system adopted in the name of Sufficiency Economy. So, as the Japan adopted Buddhist Economics naming Soka Gakki for the new way of developing the country that has been launching for every development activities The other

countries with strong Buddhist influences, like Japan, have also seen economists develop systems that incorporate Buddhist principles like "right livelihood" and the idea of a "middle way" between capitalism and socialism. However the Buddhist Economics becoming gradually popular in the global spectrum.

Chapter –II: Methodology, Objectives and Limitation of the Study:

2.1 Introducing the way of study: Obviously, this study based on the descriptive ways consulting the books and periodicals to reach to the concluding writing with full of confidence, with the objective to present the right account of the community village where people may live with full of satisfaction working together going on the management of Asta Ja (Eight Ja) resources learning the lesson of Buddha Astanga Marga. Identifying the resources human resource must keep going on working after the learning of the lesson of Ashtanga Marga (Eightfold Path). Then again, the study concentrating illustrating the unique part of Kathmandu Valley and also some governmental Issues abroad.

A brief study undertaken through the way of visiting the monastery, and interviewing the legendary

Objective of the study: Major objective of the study is to analyze the present day's problem to reach to the point of solution in the globe for the maintenance of peace through the ways of managing particular model livelihood center Model Village, either that may designed under the management of Hindu Temple, Buddha Monastery, and any other social places where community people may live peacefully satisfying their needs comfortable becomes the objectives of the study. Like in the same way some details of the objectives given in the following points as:

- To study the resources mentioned in Asta Ja (Eight Ja) framework, that could be used for production of the products that could be used by the community village for the satisfaction of community people. Presentation of the model where community people particularly living in the Gumba, and other residential management as that could be just as the Shanga of the Buddha's time, naming it the model village, where every people may be living peacefully by learning the lesson of Buddha Ashtanga Marga (Eightfold Path) to present themselves they are the noble community members working together in the community.
- Introducing the contributing personality working for the management of socio-economic sectors providing services to the people at large.
- Establishing the holistic approach to work with the people satisfying their need through their own combined effort in their model village.
- Produce quality products from organic farming that may keep satisfy the community people, and sending that in the national and international market, to get satisfactorily the return form their investment.
- Provide employment opportunity to the youths by giving them free education, free health services in the premises of the Gumba, and the model village surroundings.
- Youths from the model village community not to be going outside countries even to sell their labor, they all must be working in their own locality with reasonable remuneration.

Methodology: Methodology has been, applied for the study is descriptive presentation in language. Further comparison the views of the sectors would be analyze with simple descriptive simply presenting in pictures and

model that may give clear concept of Model Village. With the study of the economic behavior of the society that could be analyzed how they are satisfied from the management of resources working together for production. Participant's observation, face-to-face interviews, interaction and member checking are some processes to find how the Model Village Program would be launching with the utilization of Asta Ja (Eight Ja) resources with the right direction of Ashtanga Marga (Eightfold Path) for the achievement for the achievement of every development program of the government.

Consultation with Ang Temba and monks in living in the Gumba, to know the condition how they used to be living in the Monastery premises. In the Baudhanath periphery their different welfare activities performing in the monastery, also studied through the reading of the brochure of the monastery and the reading the documents in their library and also inquiring to the local residence who used to be visiting to the monastery.

In addition, description specifying Buddhist Economy, and its impact how the people residing there feeling in the monastery surroundings by reading books on Buddhism, magazines, newspapers, and many of the references have been taken to know all about the monastery what gone to study so far. With the matters whatever find there and the historic account reading from the books this study just completed with the conclusion to start the same Utpala Model community kitchen and organic market in the other parts of the country and abroad.

2.3. Limitation of the Study: This study mentioned about the designing of Model Village in the entire human world for the right livelihood of the people living in the particular community but that's not possible to go through in this brief sketch of the aspiration of the model. So, that this study merely presents a model structure establishing by the sherpa community especially they are the follower of Buddha working hard to present a model. The same articulating as to the ways of Buddhist Economics, that may significantly useful for the improvement of socio-economic system of the entire world adopting the Buddhist Economics that may keep people disciplined who could be desiring to stop war and terror in the world maintaining peace in the human world.

Chapter –III: 3.1 Asta Ja itself is what?: Asta ja is definitely new movement for economic transformation from poverty to richness, from unskilled to skillfulness, dispossession to abundances. This will certainly helpful to create the employment opportunity to the people especially the youngster who used to be trying to search to sell their labor in the Gulf and other outside countries in the world. With such right surrounding all the youth and the people able to be working for their own could-be adopting the program Asta Ja (Eight Ja) they would be supporting to the national economy that may become successfully achieve the goal of sustainable development.

To begin with, the concept publishing an article in the international journal desc (Eight Ja) framework by Professor Dr. D. Paudel while working with the Asta Ja group in Kathmandu becoming a popular concept even to the foreign countries. What is a Asta-Ja? Actually, the Asta Ja are: Jal (water); Jamin (land); Jungle (forest);, Jadibuti (medicinal and aromatic plants); Jarajuri (plants); Jalabayu (climate);Janawar (animals); Janasakti (manpower); that's all are identified naming them with Ja, of Nepali vernacular as in the form given herewith. The concept becoming a scientific model just trying to be replicated in the countries wherever they had just received the framework of Asta Ja because this concept was published an article written by D. D. Paudel in the international journals. The concept proved as it was highlighted as of the best techniques of resource utilization for income generating purpose that may keep leading the national development in the developing countries and allover.

Therefore, the Asta Ja group is very confident on the application of this concept what would be one of the right measure to reduce poverty of the nation, through the adoption of the program certainly emerging out from the poverty raising their livelihood within two decades.

Because of that Asta Ja definitely becoming one of the extra ordinary thinking for this millennium, which has been clamming with its tremendous sets of activities in the production sectors. It has made new way for the society living in different culture and religion with the identity as a citizen of the country. The concept has given definitely a new visions for how to work together to fulfill the needs such as food, shelter and clothing which are the basic requirements for all and at the same time by keeping their cultural identity intact. The Asta Ja not only fulfills the basic needs, but also gives the ways to cope to reduce the the changing scarcity in the society even for daily survival through more knowledgeable activities-for the maintenance of right livelihood.

As the resources could be identified properly through the concept of Asta Ja (Eight Ja), there the need arising how to manage the resources in the nature, who stands to manage properly?. Definitely, the manager of the resources becomes the human resource taking from the Asta Ja (Eight Ja) framework for the development to identify, utilize and conserve the resources becomes the human resource itself. Therefore, if human resource developed by giving the lesson of As-tanga Marga of Buddha they would be skilful to utilize the resources while utilizing for the production of right and quality product from the utilization of the resources.

3.2. Astanga Marga for Human Resource Development: Resource utilization is the challenging task of human beings tha€s from the eight picked up to give skill how they become able to change the matters that may worth use of human being. If perfectly utilized the resources that could be changing into valuable products becomes a means of income even for the rural people. Every individual in society must come to be able to manage the remaining resources for a better living. So, human resources must be developed by giving the lesson of Asta Marga (eightfold path) of Buddha that makes human being perfect to manage resources. Human Resources must be prepared by giving the lesson of Asta Marga (Eightfold Path) of Buddha. 1. Samyak Dristi- Samma Ditthi (Righ View)

- **Samyak Sankalpa-Samma Samkappa (Right Intention):**
- **Samyak Bachan -Samma Vaca (Right Speech)**
- **Samyak Karma -Samma Kammanta (Right Action)**
- **Samyak Abas -Samma Ajiva (Right livelihood)**
- **Samyak Prayas- Samma Vayama (Right Effort)**
- **Samyak Manobhav -Samma Sati (Right Mindfulness) and**
- **Samyak Samadhi - Samma Samadhi (Right Concentration)**

Buddha manage his disciple to live in the Sangha (Community) that has now been named a Model Village community where community people in that particular community live to learn the lesson to manage the resources to become right disciplined in the Asta Marg of Buddha. After receiving skill to bring changes in raw resources into the product that could be used in the community may keep all well satisfied with the use of the same products produced by the skillful energetic and disciplined human resources perfectly.

Consequently, human resource learning the lesson of Astanga Marga of Buddha, would be rightly skillfully to use the resources producing quality products for the satisfaction of community people living in efferent Model Village Community. Relating to manage the community living for the people for their peaceful settlement, there the need arising what would be the model for right livelihood. From the categorical set of Astanga Marga, the right livelihood picked up by the prominent writer of the Book Small is Beautiful, there he defined the Buddhist Economist at first, by E. F. Schumacher Accordingly, he defined the right livelihood adopting the concept of Buddhist Economy where every member of the community become fully satisfied working together in their community. As of the concept of E. F. Schumacher and, under William Henry Beveridge, the chief economic adviser to the government, worked on plans for Britain’s postwar welfare state. From 1950 to 1970 he was also an adviser to Britain’s nationalized coal industry. E. F. Schumacher mentioned the Buddhist Economics and he has given the way how to manage the right livelihood for community living just that was designed in the time of Buddha to manage to live for his disciples, forming a Sangha. Accordingly here mentioned as of in the same way that is Model Village where community people living together properly utilizing the resources for production there what they produced would be of the matter for the full satisfaction of the community members equally. So, as the Model Village could be formed in every country in the globe.

Model Village Community Development Program: Model village program started since last some year's considering to present model to the people living together, working for the utilization of the Resources mentioned in the Asta Ja (Eight Ja) framework for overall development. There might be designed several Model Village in the countries that may extending all over the entire world. The community settlement just based on the concept of Buddhist Economics that was mentioned by the E.F. Schumacher in his book Small is Beautiful that could be replicated to the other parts. It's a concept brought for creating competitive environment among and between for the enhancement of the production movement. To keep pace forward we have been working in the following program in different places as shown in the diagram:

Fig. 6: Model Village Development Committee *Figure -I*

The above model indicates all the sector of the economy in the community level must be actively working jointly for the modification of their community village that has been now naming Model Village community.

Chapter – IV: 4.1 Strategy to Manage the Eight Resources: The various researches indicated that management of eight resources (i.e., Ja) is not easy task. Even the developed economies there seems not been able to use all the resources in the optimum level because of that sometimes they are facing financial turmoil's ultimately unrest in the economic system over there. Small country like Switzerland, Japan and Singapore have managed somehow maximum level and proved that they are capable in maintaining higher rate of development even though they are small countries as compared to USA, Russia, China and Australia. In such a scenario, Nepal can do and manage to work for development by using these resources properly. Because, it is underdeveloped economy and it has to do lot for development and create an employment opportunity in the country. Therefore, the study has going to point out the strategic model for use of these resources, which are as follows:

Development a model of Management: Initially, the concept of Eight Ja has been originated as it's a right model in the discussion of the group of Asta Ja Abhiyan Nepal (Eight Ja Movement Nepal). For the expansion of this concept Dr. D. D. Paudel supported to the movement for its expansion. The model has clearly defined how it works when it implemented scientifically. Thus, the Asta Ja managements' as an input, process and output could be depicted as a system in the figure I:

Figure -II

As in the managerial model of eight Ja figured on the above shows the input process and output goes as a process until to achieve from the utilization of resources the outcome which is highly technical. While defining the Asta Ja management topics as system, we usually see and seek all about the process and the way how we could achieve the targeted result. Now mere the targeted result becomes a few because we have to receive much within a short period of time if we are aiming at the reach the progress of the others doing in the world. Therefore, the change,

change, and change all the repeated word within a second think driving you when and where you are working. You are even at home any time anyway you would be sleeping you must think how you could achieve what in the right the moment. It is because, you have to reach or meet the personality movement who could achieve the objective conquering the space already. Therefore the process as described earlier could be conceptualized by some briefing in the following:

Thinking: It becomes the way what, how and where questions push every moment to make us thinking. Accordingly think positively and work for result; because there are four types of personality you find in the society, there you have to seek where you are? As we know the categorically the person like he/she is:

Grave Fire: In the category here the person thinks everywhere the situation is not coping for success, and thinks I am too not good along with the people remaining all. So, such has been called crow personality. If we present at work alike could not achieve any result even for him/her selves.

Crow Personality: In this category a person thinks I am all right but remaining all are worst so how can I achieve the goal alone. Saying he becomes autocratic and tries to drive all but fails is his crow personality always crying, crying, and crying.

Candle Light: This personality refers to the persons apart from him/her are all correct and working rightly, tries how to be like them to achieve the goal of the organization. The personality in this category is candle light, if one burning, burns remaining others. So, such personalities are called candle light one.

Tube Light: This is the last and perfect quality of personality that in need in any places and any organization to lead to receive desirable result, it is because the personality thinks I am right and the remaining are also right at working and we should work together. The great psychologists are in rest on the last point now it has been described.

Thinking should be positive and to have think for winning all in the competition to produce some and make available the product for all. If you think to produce for enjoy yourself, it couldn't have much achievement and such thinking would make you ruined again and think it is little progressive from remaining idle but not much pleasant one. The veteran and successful business personality Mr. Bill Gate says as " sow a thought reap and action, sow an action reap a habit, sow a habit reap a character, sow a character reap the destiny". So, we all have to reach to the destiny for all achievement. Without achievement, we can't have destiny with us.

If you think positively you may assured to success, at the same time you achieve almost half of the target. So you have to be creative every moment putting and making the way how the society in trouble comes up with humanitarian ground with your support. If you could reach to the point of thinking, you yourself could be achieving a lot unknowingly. Positive thinking would make you perfect planner to create a beautiful world. You need to think clearly that you should not be the promoter of death. You should be promoter of happiness and success for mankind. Therefore, you have to promote such type of activities which would relate to achievement of productivity for development. The figure-1 clearly shows interrelationship of the activities. Further, the figure –II shows for more specific for implementation which is as follows:

The above figure generates several arguments for discussion, here some may say it's worthless, or some other may put their view it's the way of thinking in the school of management. So, the purpose of putting such model here is to create a way to think of own way to describe management, through what Asta Ja (Eight Ja) could be adopted for the development of the Model Village Community as well as the nations in the entire world

Creating a way for Implementation: Thinking, if it used in practice becomes perfects and creates a new again and again. If it left unused, it could be waste of time, and energy. Its application is indeed a phenomenon which could be everyone realize. So, what you are thinking, you should try to bring its implementation immediately as we have brought in the Asta Ja for implementation in the different activities. As earlier said that we should be the promoter of happiness and development rather it would be the promoter of death. It could be a controversial

statement here now, because why and how we lie on working to promote the death? It's easy to say if we sank on corruption, smuggling, vandalism, quarreling, wasting time and energy and so on will be promoting death and destruction. Instead going in the brink of collapse we need to be corrected by adopting the Buddhist Economic System.

Ignoring all such negativism, if we devote for creation a new way of life, it will certainly bring the happiness in the society and at the same time it beautifies the nation. In this way, it will promote the development that surely change for comfort of the society equally. Therefore, Asta Ja has come to implement the concept in practice in the society going to seek and develop entrepreneurship in each and every individual in the country and in the world at large.

4.2 Entrepreneurship Development: Think the society itself an enterprise where various creativities exist because members in the society find working in different way for their survival. On such a wonderful phenomenon, one specific person who tries to do something a new way would make the other people happy from their working environment with the change on their stepping subject to providing the skill and support for their activities. Therefore, we can see entrepreneur in two ways as:

Business Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurs in business activities are self-motivating personality who could go for creating a new way to start firm for their own benefit at the same time he is giving a new think which is beneficial for the society as well. They are not the job seeker but they are the job giver and creator of wealth for the national development. The personality if so they involving actively working in the society are generally may come to be few in numbers and they are called owner or the business holders for instance the owner of Bhat Bhateni Super Market, World Trade Market, Civil Mal owner, and farm developer in different farming land to produce commercial agricultural production come to the front. Such types of entrepreneurs fall on the category of business entrepreneurship.

Social Entrepreneurship: Social entrepreneurship is quite different as compared to business entrepreneurship. The identification such entrepreneur in this category is not easy, because we have to go on seeking everyone in the society that are in what type of service holders providing in the society from their business. In this category, the entrepreneur are actually providing skill and promoting them to work to raise the standard of living on their own resource mobilization skim for the society. Such types of entrepreneurial works could be seen in the cooperatives, agricultural production groups, and clubs through healthy competition in different activities and in different characters in the society. Asta Ja management goes to the society beautifully creating social entrepreneurship by promoting productive sectors. To see the social entrepreneurship model we have to go for some steps as it has been described below:

Leadership Development: Social group can't bring into action without the guidance of leaders of its own and they are chosen by themselves. If a social community has a perfect, the competent leader from all the members involve could be going to learn different skill for income generation activities and they can earn for their own sake.

Leadership Application: After the development of the leadership skill, it is to be applied properly in the community's activities to promote them for working and mobilization of resources in their own. It will generate the income by creating new environment to develop their entrepreneurship level. The need brings invention and innovation which comes urgently and enables them to start a new venture. Even it may fall on a small level. Considering the seriousness situation of rural poor, the leader has to work with them at least to raise their level of income and the standard of living.

Competition of the Leadership Activities: Application of the leadership skill in the community starts working perfectly and it seems the result from working. The activities automatically goes smoothly for competition, observation of development certainly that effects to adjacent villages and others places too which there will be ultimately supporting the national development. If competition goes on and on the community, the society becomes stronger together with the entrepreneur development in the members as well. At last, with such activities social entrepreneurship could be nicely functioning in the society.

Standardization of the Leadership Activities: After the process comes a success on competition leaders scales up to become standard in the community level and people say that's the model of leadership we should follow everywhere. The popularity of the Asta ja leaders learning the lesson of Buddha Astanga Marga, through that the community encouraged to work together that vigorously achieving the large scale of production targeting to reach the village as a model of entrepreneurial activities.

Socialization of Leadership Activities: This stage of social development and leadership is the destiny to reach any way that makes all the happiness to the people by receiving everything for them. Production whatever they do would be distributed as required by the community members. All the members become satisfied with their own activities because they had physically seen their actual benefit from the entrepreneurship development.

Thinking all about the concept: The Asta Ja Management strategy as it is described by presenting some models could not be enough even at this juncture. However, it could be a matter of satisfaction for initiating in this topic at least. There are so many successful examples in this issue. However, the study trying to prescribe success of some example in the society is as follows:

4.3 Case of Nepal: The government of Nepal has tried to show the world community how they could come to be consciously working on the climate and environment change and its effect in the human life. The cabinet meeting of 21 members of Nepal held in the Kalapathar the base camp of Everest at the height of 17,192ft., from the sea level on 4th Dec 2009 to indicating their concern and to make the people conscious for the protection of glacier that provides the natural energy to the living beings on the earth. The cabinet has immediately decided to make action plan and the message for world community is clear that immediate action should be taken for conservation and protection of environment from the degradation of climate and environment change, which are as follows:

- **Working together with other nations**
- **Launch mass awareness**
- **Address negative impact of climate change**
- **Preserving the mountain ecosystem**

- Global support for projects
- Reduction in C emission
- Clean Development Mechanism
- Calls for maintaining the level of GHG and global temperatures
- Research on glacial retreat
- Call for reducing GHG and compensation

Figure IV

Case of Maldives: Similarly Maldives conducted a historic meeting under the water on 20th October 2009 to decide how to be safe from the dangers of the rising sea level. Maldivian president Mohammed Nasheed and his ministers signed a document calling on all countries to cut their carbon dioxide emissions for the protection of climate all over in the meeting held for 30 minutes less than six meters deep from the sea. The nation's president Mohammed Nasheed has voiced fears the archipelago will be swamped by raising sea levels unless action is taken to reduce carbon emissions. Three of the 14 in the cabinet members had to miss the underwater meeting because

two were not given medical permission and another was abroad. This meeting was focusing the future of the 350,000 inhabitants of the country live on 1,192 coral islands an average of only 2.1 meters above the ocean always facing for fears of rising the level of the water in the sea. The picture taken into the sea puts the fact how it was held:

Figure V:

These are some of the cases related to effect of environment and climate change in the earth to be shown the concern to make aware the world community. The world community has signed the **Kyoto Protocol** which is actually United Nations Framework for Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC or FCCC). The **Kyoto Protocols'** main aim is to fight against global warming. The UNFCCC is actually an international environment treaty with the goal of achieving the "stabilization of greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent danger anthropogenic interference with the earth's climate system. This protocol initially adopted on 11th December 1997 in Kyoto, Japan, and entered into force on 16th February 2005. The 191 states have signed and ratified the Kyoto Protocol in September 2011. Similarly, Canada renounced the Protocol in December 2011. However, the only one developed country, the United States of America remains to signature and ratify the Protocol at present. Similarly, the under developed countries and United Nation member of states: Afghanistan, Andorra and South Sudan are not signed and ratified the Kyoto Protocol agreement till date.

Chapter –V: 5.1 Conclusion: The movement of Asta Ja (Eight Ja) has been a challenging concept if adopted everywhere that may change the society living in terrible atmosphere would be living in full comfort. However the confusion remaining in among the administrator and the intellectuals must come to be aware on the environment that may improve adopting the Buddhist Economics. If so everywhere this concept expended, all the community members of the Model Village Community would be motivated then only the people for collective

benefit they virtually harvesting the fruit of real achievement that expecting yet to be seen. The group is very much optimistic of its outcome in the long period which will certainly create the environment for everyone should be involved to do such creative work for them. There are plenty of resources left unused in the country and same are yet to be explored. A the same time, the nation has been seeking the way out how to be achieved just seeking outside sources by selling labor, and asking donation from other friendly nations to meet the objective of national development since last many decades. The government and leaders are in dilemma that they are proud of receiving donation from world community and sending youths other friendly countries to sale their labor becoming a curse of the society in such backward countries. In such scenario, the movement of Asta Ja (Eight Ja) learning the lesson of Buddha Astanga Marga (Eightfold Path), adopting Buddhist Economics, may make a big change the leaders, economists, bureaucrats' and Nepalese communities pre mind set of present economic system and start to think new way of Asta Ja Group working style of national development and achieve the improvement of employment at the same time identify, utilize, and conserve the resources available in our country.

Conceptual framework just designing with the desire of every prosperity equally sharing among the people could be the same defined in this text: Asta Ja (Eight Ja) resource management framework. Then to go for proper management of the resources, there the need arising to make human resources well skilful to use the resources for production of the quality products that may well satisfy the people equally in the globe becomes to learn the lesson of Buddha Astanga Marga. Then the full satisfaction of the people might be assured with that assurance sustainable development goal could be achieve with the management of social, economic and environmental perspectives. Then only the Model Village would be rightly managed with full satisfaction among the community members. Lastly the great desire to manage the peace in the human world would be confirmed what becoming very basic effort for overall development. The following model gives the clear pictures how to manage every component, for the maintenance of peace in the human world:

Figure: IV:

The Group of Asta Ja (Eight Ja) movement has defined all the resources in eight category are equally strong to generate employment, income, and everything for the development of the nation. If the instances of the forest and plants we are using naturally receiving oxygen on the volume in calculation present days price it accounts Rs. 2100 per day and Rs.7,66,500 per year and the life span of the people now it is 65 years the total consumption worth Rs. 5,00,00,000 without paying. Such valuable products regularly we are receiving from the nature and we can have better result if we go for identifying, utilizing and conserving the resources what we deriving and utilizing from the nature. Asta Ja Abhiyan Nepal is working for making results from the resources that are available in the local level. Therefore management strategy of Asta Ja Abhiyan Nepal wouldn't be enough with the description herein. It goes for many setting and studying for long even it is important for overall development and economic transformation of the country and in the entire world. The Asta Ja Group are very much conscious to make short term and long term planning so that the optimum employment and off course ultimately sustainable national development will be achieved.

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